

Ways to improve the integration of pedagogical technologies in the education process.

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Abstract: *The development of a new education system based on our people’s rich spiritual potential and the latest achievements of universal values, modern culture, science and technology is increasingly important. Successful implementation of the goals and objectives set by our people in raising the building of a humane, democratic, legal state and society to a higher level of socio-economic and cultural development, recognized in the normative documents in force in our country, is important for our country to take its rightful place in the world community.*

Key words: *education, nationality, modernization, honesty, alternative curricula, design, pedagogical technologies*

After the independence of our country, deep reforms have been carried out in the economic, political, spiritual and cultural spheres, and the results of these reforms are clearly visible today. Successful implementation of the goals and objectives set by our people in raising the building of a humane, democratic, legal state and society to a higher level of socio-economic and cultural development, recognized in the normative documents in force in our country, is important for our country to take its rightful place in the world community. In carrying out these huge tasks, it is planned to train competitive specialists as a result of providing comprehensive and thorough knowledge to the younger generation, which is the foundation of the country's development. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 “On the Strategy for further development of the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, June 5, 2018 “Improving the quality of education in higher education and ensuring their active participation in comprehensive reforms in the country” Resolution No. PP-3775 of September 5,

2018 “On additional measures to improve the management system of public education” and Decree No. PF-5538 “On additional measures to improve the management of public education” and other regulations related to this activity. The essence of the goals and objectives of education is fully defined. At the same time, serious shortcomings in the education system include: “the lack of independent thinking skills in students due to shortcomings in the educational process and teaching methods in schools and universities; practical orientation of general secondary education, formation of labor skills, insufficient level of professional orientation; lack of objectivity and speed in the system of management and assessment of students' learning activities; The low level of knowledge and professionalism of a large number of teachers, educators and educators.

In addition, paragraph 4 of the Action Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 “On further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” sets a number of tasks for the development of education and science from the priorities of the social sphere; It is important to continue to improve the system of continuing education, increase the capacity of quality educational services, train highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market.

In the third stage of the “National Training Program” (2005 and beyond), “further strengthening of the resource, personnel and information base of educational institutions, the full provision of the educational process with new teaching materials, advanced pedagogical technologies” was.

Based on the tasks set, there are significant changes in today's education system, modernized educational standards, new generation textbooks, varied curricula, improved programs have been created and delivered to schools. The material and technical base has been strengthened at all levels of the education system, new buildings of educational institutions have been built, the existing ones have been renovated, modern equipment, technical means and computers have been provided. Measures aimed at improving the financial situation of pedagogical scientists, teachers, educators, coaches working in the system of higher and

secondary special education, preschool education institutions are being consistently implemented. So, in our country, all the conditions are being created for the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation at the level of modern requirements and their comprehensive development.

An important factor in the successful solution of urgent tasks facing our society in the future is to ensure that employees of the system of continuing education, teachers master modern educational technologies, be able to use them effectively in the educational process.

It should be noted that today in the pedagogical literature the ideas aimed at the introduction of pedagogical technologies are often repeated, therefore, the concepts of “new pedagogical technology”, “advanced pedagogical technology” are increasingly used. Therefore, the rapid introduction of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process and its effectiveness has become a modern requirement.

It is known from the literature that the idea of technologicalization of the education system appeared in the early twentieth century in the early years of the movement to reform the education system in Western Europe and the United States. The idea of “technologicalization” entered the educational process as a “pedagogical technique” in the 30s, and in the 50s and 60s, views on this concept increased. In countries such as the United States, England, Japan and Italy, educational technology research institutions, publications - scientific magazines appeared. These institutions and journals have been active in researching, summarizing, and disseminating research on educational technology. In recent years, with the help of these organizations, centers of pedagogical technology have been established at a number of universities, pedagogical scientists, advanced teachers began to conduct research on the problem of pedagogical technology, the study of pedagogical technology in schools and vocational education. actively assisted in their work.

The UNESCO definition of “pedagogical technology” is as follows: “Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining

knowledge, taking into account the technical and personal resources and their interaction, which sets the task of effective forms of education in the process of teaching and learning.”

Today, the country has accumulated a number of experiences on “Pedagogical technology”, and the number of teaching aids that generalize such experiences is growing. New pedagogical technologies are gradually being studied by our teachers working in all spheres of the education system and are being rapidly introduced into the pedagogical process. At the same time, of course, methodical associations in educational institutions, seminars in the district department of public education, courses conducted at the city, regional, republican teacher training and retraining institutes play a significant role.

The number of advanced teachers who are conducting open lessons in educational institutions using new pedagogical technologies and informing the teaching staff about the news is also growing. Along with the current problems of pedagogy, pedagogical scientists are conducting extensive research on new pedagogical technologies and advanced interactive teaching methods.

Thus, pedagogical technology is a pre-designed educational process of theoretically based forms, methods and techniques of education and upbringing, which allows to achieve the set educational goals and objectives. The main problem in pedagogical technology is to choose the most goal-oriented from the organizational forms, methods and techniques of education.

The renewal and growth of social needs in human life, in turn, requires the establishment of activities that ensure their short-term and quality satisfaction. Improvement of educational technologies, which are a product of social necessity, allows to achieve high quality results in a short period of time with little physical effort.

Educational technologies cover a certain area of pedagogical activity. The pedagogical approach creates new opportunities in the conceptual and project development of various areas of educational, pedagogical, social activities. For example:

- high-precision recording of results and effective management of the pedagogical process;

- scientific analysis and application of existing practical experience;

- integrated solution of educational and socio-educational problems;

- providing favorable conditions for personal development;

- reducing the impact of inconveniences on people;

- rational use of resources;

- development of effective new technologies in accordance with the national model of training, solving socio-pedagogical problems, etc.

One of the important requirements in the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short period of time without excessive mental and physical effort. Delivering certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short period of time, developing skills and competencies in a particular activity, as well as monitoring student performance, assessing the level of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by them requires high pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process.

As the essence of modern education is modern pedagogical technologies, it is important to have a comprehensive understanding of its classification. The classification of pedagogical technologies includes the analysis of their appearance, levels, pedagogical technologies.

It is known that when the purpose of education is abstract, uncertain, the student loses interest in learning, teachers, parents often complain about the lack of interest of children in reading. It is not difficult to know the reason for this. This is because, first of all, the answer to the question of what I am reading to the child, the knowledge that the teacher is describing, what the content of the lesson gives me, should be clearly demonstrated in the course of the lesson.

It is no secret that if a student fails to complete a task, it is considered a consequence of the child's low intelligence, frustration, low ability. In fact, no one remembers that a teacher's learning process is boring, insensitive, unexciting.

As a result, the one-hour lesson for children is not well mastered. The reason is the boring organization of the lesson, the lack of creativity and skill in the teacher.

The phrase “if the lesson is difficult - the student falls asleep” is used for such lessons.

So, now is the time to organize the educational process on the basis of updated standards, programs, textbooks. In other words, a teacher who takes a responsible approach to the organization of lessons instead of boring lessons, has deep knowledge and skills in their field, is well versed in modern educational technologies, is able to achieve good results in the educational process using appropriate and effective interactive teaching methods demand is growing. After all, any education is focused on the personality of the student, his desires and needs, in short, every lesson is effective only if the student participates in each lesson with enthusiasm. In order to achieve the effectiveness of the lesson, it is necessary to master the modern technologies of education.

Every educator who wants to achieve the effectiveness of the lesson, first of all, designs the lesson in accordance with the purpose. It is advisable to make the content of the lesson clear and interesting on the basis of this project.

Design is one of the important conditions for the organization of the pedagogical process and its successful conduct. In designing the pedagogical process:

- 1) analysis of the content of pedagogical activity;
- 2) to get results in advance;
- 3) creation of a project for the implementation of the planned activities.

The design of the pedagogical process is the implementation of education that serves to integrate the overall essence of pedagogical activity, organized on the basis of the project → content → trinity of activities.

The introduction of new technologies into the educational process has its own mechanisms. With the bold and effective use of such mechanisms of pedagogical

technology, each school should plan its future activities for the introduction of pedagogical technology.

As we mentioned above, no matter how positive pedagogical technology is in achieving educational effectiveness, it is not correct to understand it as a single system, but as much as the teaching process requires creativity from the teacher, pedagogical technology requires a more creative approach, enriching its methods and techniques.

Today, a number of developed countries have accumulated valuable experience in the application of pedagogical technologies in the educational process, and the methods used in these experiments are becoming more widespread under the name of interactive methods.

It is known that in education based on modern pedagogical technology, the creative pursuits of students should be taken into account. The main task of the modern educational process is to consider the student not only as an executor of the teacher's order, but also as a subject of learning, opening the way for their free, independent and creative thinking. Such an approach to education, in turn, is a guarantee of achieving educational effectiveness. In the organization of the learning process on the basis of educational technologies, there are several interrelated stages of acquisition of knowledge, which determine the level of knowledge and understanding of the situation, such as the transfer of ready knowledge to the mind, recollection, recollection, narration, written expression. . A problem-based approach is important to require the learner to take a creative approach at certain levels, to apply what students have learned at later levels of mastery, to achieve, supplement, enrich, master, and to have their own independent perspective.

Such a systematic approach to the learning process is a measure of the guaranteed achievement of the effectiveness of the activities of the participants, and the learning process depends on how accurately the perception of reality is perceived.

Interactive methods from modern educational technologies are widely used in the educational process. These include “Art Education Technology”, “Cooperative TT”, “Integrated Education T”, “Team Creative Work Technology”, “Health Education Technology”, “Health Trainings”, “Neurolinguistic Programmed Technology”, “Reflexive Learning Technology”, “Vitagen Education technology”, “Contextual learning technology”, “Module credit learning technology”, “Networking technology” and others are widely used interactive methods.

When it comes to interactive methods, it should be noted that modern technologies are the product of the creativity of pedagogical scientists, practicing teachers, and their introduction into the pedagogical process requires the effective and appropriate use of various interactive methods.

The effectiveness of the educational process requires the use of modern pedagogical technologies, pre-design of the studied material, that is, to determine how to solve the content, goals and objectives. Indeed, the essence of pedagogical technology is that any complex educational system is designed by connecting it with practice, taking into account the scientific, convenient, continuous, promising results. Because the effectiveness of the use of any pedagogical technology depends on the variability, the design of the educational process, its model, organizational principles, methods and techniques, tools, conditions, forms of organization.

In this regard, Lawrence Staut, a professor at the Stockholm School of Economics in Riga, cites seven key principles for improving educational efficiency:

1. Education is based on cooperation. Mutual trust between the teacher and the student is of great importance, and the teacher must be able to instill a sense of trust in the student with his knowledge and skills in this regard.
2. The learning process is a natural process in which information is received and perceived. The learning process takes place in a natural environment and the learner should be directed to the learning process naturally, not necessarily.

3. Knowledge is the most necessary feeling. Knowing is everyone's inner need. The most necessary requirements for a person are food, security, love, and most importantly, self-expression, if necessary. But the need to understand and know is the basis of these five requirements.

In other words, reading and learning is a necessity of life for everyone, and he lives by striving to fight for it.

4. Everyone has their own individual characteristics. Accordingly, even the most skilled teacher is not able to fully realize the effectiveness of teaching, because every student acquires knowledge at different levels.

The effectiveness of education also depends on the teacher's ability to teach and work with each student individually.

5. Reading is continuous work. Only deep and solid knowledge can be obtained through conscious active labor activity. But it is necessary to convince the student that he can succeed as a result of trying to work actively. The student needs to learn to work continuously so that he can enjoy reading, rather than being indifferent to his work and indifferent to reading.

6. It is known that everyone is considered social. He feels the need for other people to live and work well. The same is true of reading. If a student lives and reads in an environment where he or she feels the need to read, reading will be valuable and enjoyable to him or her.

7. Education should be in strong connection with practice. This is the most important of all the principles. True, there is, of course, theoretical information in education. But every theoretical rule must be applied in practice.

The above principles require the teacher to use different tools in the learning process, the knowledge imparted to be clear, understandable, the student to actively participate in the learning process, to be satisfied with their success, the teacher to bring to the attention of the student, both actively interact with each other.

This interaction can increase the effectiveness of education and continue in the future.

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